

AUTISM. WORKING WITH AUTISTIC CHILDREN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7556798>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11th January 2023

Accepted: 19th January 2023

Online: 21th January 2023

KEY WORDS

Autism, symptoms, genes, child, parents, inheritance, communication, social, memory, non-medical, teaching.

ABSTRACT

This article is primarily intended for school teachers and discusses how to teach people with Autism.

INTRODUCTION: Human body is so complicated that scientists cannot fully comprehend it for centuries. Why is it so complex? First of all, human being cannot be explored in a lab. Since, having felt observed, people tend to be more artificial, as brain feels “uneasy” by the process. Secondly, it is gen code. They keep mutating, duplicating, inverting even deleting. Nobody could predict, how gens would mutate with each other. Although, does it feel so messy that scientists cannot fully understand, humans’ brain is so organized to monitor the whole body by creating strong strategy.

Today, due to those mutations of gens, there are countless illnesses, syndromes, disorders and etc. One of them is Autism Spectrum disorder (ASP) which has been developing drastically in the past decade. Today, about 1 in 54 children are diagnosed with autism, and many of them can attend regular classes.

METHODOLOGY: In fact, Autism Spectrum Disorder is untreatable, and “Spectrum” means it may differ from person to person. However, education somehow assist children with this disorder. Depending on child’s “symptoms”, teacher could find way to improve their weaknesses through teaching.

1. The first to mention is that autistic people are straightforward. They may face obstacles when it comes to long verbal instructions, as it is arduous to recall the sequences for them. It is better to write them down or simplification of the steps, especially, for the schedules.

2. Research has showed that more than 80% of autistic individuals are visual learners. Utilizing visual materials and videos can improve the comprehension of the specific topic. Additionally, visual materials should be concrete, comprehensive in order not to challenge the learners. Other potential issues may be usage of colors or light. While using the videos sound on, some students may face less tolerance on some kind of sound (often times repetitive sounds), which should also be taken into account.

3. Autistic people tend to have privilege in art, musical instruments or in computer programming. If those talents are developed, they will turn into skills, which may provide advantage in the future.

4. In today's fast-forwarding world, multitasking has been becoming more popular. However, most of the autistic children may experience difficulties while multitasking, for instance, they cannot concentrate on teacher's speech and visual materials simultaneously. So, it is advisable to recognize child's abilities beforehand. Depending on that, teachers may use specific methods.

5. One of the things which autistic people may find difficult or overwhelming is social skills. Social skills are one of the major when it comes to diagnose autistic adult. So, preparing them unpredicted or unexpected social communication may be hard for their educators, as autistic people tend to avoid from this kind of situations.

6. Non-verbal communication is also somehow difficult for children with autism. Avoiding from eye contact, repetitive actions, non-comprehensive body language can be improved by teachers by right methods and creating comfortable condition for learners.

CONCLUSION: Autism is non-medical condition. Autistic people have their own world and patterns. Even though, autistic children may lack sometimes or differ from others, they can obtain many achievements in their life by the help of their teachers. Additionally, not only teachers, but whole society should support them in preparation for bigger life.

References:

1. Author Casey Ames. What is the history of Autism Spectrum disorder? (2018, March 30). Retrieved from <https://harkla.co/blogs/special-needs/history-of-autism/>
2. Author Dr. Crystal I. Lee. Different, not deficient: Autism and communication in people. Retrieved from <https://laconciiergepsychologist.com/blog/autism-communication/>
3. Author Guv Callahan. Teaching methods and strategies to enhance learning for students with Autism. (2020 October 16). Retrieved from <https://www.rev.com/blog/speech-to-text-accessibility/instructional-teaching-strategies-for-students-with-autism>
4. Author Temple Grandin. Teaching tips for children and adults with autism (2002, December). Retrieved from: <https://www.iidc.indiana.edu/irca/articles/teaching-tips-for-children-and-adults-with-autism.html>